

Strategic Planning In Libya's Higher Education System: A Theoretical Evaluation¹

Abdoulwaed Aboudaber² 0000-0003-1697-4726
 Kastamonu University Department of Management , ewhida60@gmail.com, Türkiye

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Abstract

For nearly 30 years, strategic planning researchers, advocates, and practitioners have argued that effective strategic management is a tool to improve organizational performance. They argue that this is associated with a positive relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance. They argue that strategic planning is associated with organization and environmental harmony. This is because improved financial performance, the definition of effective organizational missions, is vital to create and sustain competition. The Relationship between Strategic Planning and Performance Concepts requires that strategic planning and performance management processes be considered inseparable as two parts, when both concepts require an efficient and efficient operation. In fact, the relationship between the two concepts can be expressed quite simply. Targets are part of the strategic planning process. This study aims to understand strategic planning taking into account the present circumstances.

Keywords: Strategic Planning, University of Tripoli, Higher Education Performance

Introduction

Over the past few years, both the programs and the number of students in Libya's higher education institutions have increased dramatically. The large increase in the number of higher education institutions also has exceeded the country's needs and demands. There are many studies on this subject in the literature. The common ideas of studies are that there are many shortcomings in the current higher education system in Libya, both in performance and function. This study found that the implementation of tertiary institutions present in Libya needs to be critically evaluated. It has been noted that the implementation of higher education institutions should be addressed in a comprehensive manner. The notion of strategic planning may first be used to assert that a process that is incomplete or flawed, when it comes to the emergence of educational institutions, can be dealt with in a strategic plan. This increases the development and performance of organizations (Piorun, 2011).

Literature

Organizational performance is crucial for the organization to determine the speed of inventory turnover, clients, profitability, market share, and productivity levels. The goal of these organizations is to improve organizational performance. Because the main purpose of organizations is to make profits. And Iravo. (2013) one of the questions in business is why some organizations fail others. It is also being attempted to determine the relationship between the driving forces of organizational performance and its success. In her work published in Fwaya (2006), she sees performance as a formula for evaluating an organization under certain parameters such as operation, efficiency, motivation and effectiveness. Nzube and Nyaega (2012) argue that

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² Corresponding Author ewhida60@gmail.com

performance management and improvement are at the heart of strategic management. The reason is that many strategic ideas are aimed at identifying and measuring performance. Awino (2011) argues that an organization must achieve high returns and determine performance factors at all levels in order to be considered successful. Odhiambo (2009) argues that organizations may prefer three performance-oriented approaches. The first is the target approach (the organization pursues specific identifiable goals). Second, the system approach (which defines performance as the relationship between the organization and its surroundings) (URL-1 Access Date:01.06.2021)

He sees the main concept of performance as the ability to secure the organization's limited and valuable resources in its environment. The third approach to the process relates the performance to the behavior of the organization's human resource (Waiganjo et.al., 2012). Kiragu (2005) associates the concept of performance with four factors: financial, customer, internal processes, and innovation. The financial factor refers to financial factors for improving performance such as profit margin, asset transfer, leverage, cash flow, and operating capital (Wadongo, etc., 2010). Customer-factor performance characterizes brand image, customer satisfaction, customer retention and customer profitability. Internal processes emphasize the efficiency of the organization's system, while ultimately, innovation is the organization's potential to adapt to changing conditions. This work is based on Resource-Based Theory. According to Resource-Based Theory, strategic management and economics are closely related to each other. On the other hand, they have the power to influence each other (Barney, 1991). The other principle of this theory is that the organization's ability to compete or perform at a high level is proportional to its distinctive property (Johnson and., 2008). Resource-Based Theory primarily advocates control of the organization's valuable material or non-material resources (Penrose, 1959; Rumelt, 1984; Wernerfelt, 1984). The related theory argues that organizations must be heterogeneous and not mobile in order to turn short-term competitive advantages into a sustainable competitive advantage. What is meant by non-mobile is that they are not imitative and cannot be substituted (Barney, 1991). The strategy is a match between the organizations' own internal resources and capabilities, and the opportunities and risks created by their external environments. The organization's resources and capabilities are the fundamental issues that determine their strategies. These resources and abilities also help to establish an organization's identity.

The main objective of Resource-Based Theory is to understand relationships between resources, skills, competitive advantage, and performance. Source-based opinion has become a common interest for management science writers, and many works have been written about it. Source-Based Theory argues that if resources are administered so that they cannot be imitated by competitors, then they will be given a sustainable competitive advantage. The inability to replicate resources creates a competitive barrier for other organizations (Mahoney and Pandian, 1992). An organization will take advantage of sustainable competition because its resources are rare, valuable, imitative, non-negotiable, non-residential (Barney, 1999). Umar (2005) investigated the strategic management relationship between the merger of Nestle and Lever Brothers. A review of the study's findings finds that strategic management practices, particularly merging, have played a crucial role in the success, growth, and survival of organizations (URL-2 Access Date: 08.06.2022). In his studies Ademi (1992) he discovered a positive relationship between strategic management and organizational performance in Nigerian banks. Another researcher examined the impact of strategic management on enterprise performance in selected small businesses in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. The findings found that strategic management practices increase both corporate profitability and business market share. Thus it has been suggested that the concept of strategic planning should be strictly adopted by commercial enterprises (Dauda et.al., 2010), Fiberesima and Abdul Rani (2013) have studied the effects of strategic management on the success of organizations in their business. The study concludes that strategic management is positively associated with corporate success, and that strategic management practices are successful in business. Another work was done in Kenya by Gichunge (2007). This study also examined the relationship between strategic management and organizational performance of medium-sized manufacturing enterprises. One of the key findings of the study is the existence of a relationship between competition and strategic management.

Businesses that officially adopt strategic management are outperforming businesses that don't. Singh (2005) chose a different institution in his work. The organization favored in the study differs from non-profit. The most important finding of the study is the relationship between strategic planning and organization performance even in non-profit institutions.

In their study, Askarany and Yazdifar (2012), they examined the relationship of proposed strategic management techniques to the theory of organizational change in recent years. The relationship between organizational performance and strategic management techniques in almost all sectors of New Zealand is under scrutiny. Results show an important relationship between the adoption of new strategic management techniques and the performance of business. Owolabi and Makinde (2012) studied the effects of strategic planning on institutional performance at Babcock University in Nigeria. As a result, they demonstrated a meaningful positive relationship between strategic planning and business performance. Andrews and I. (2006) they studied the relationship between strategy and organizational performance with a variable model in which external factors were taken into account. The research consists of senior and middle-level executives from 120 organizations. The research uses a Likert-type scale. The research focuses on the relationship between strategy types and hierarchical layout. The result was that research had positive, defense neutral, and negative effects on response.

The source-based theory introduced by Barney argues that competitors cannot compete significantly with well-positioned organizations in the market and may not perform well enough to compete. In order to sustain competitiveness on the market and on the market, an organization must also utilize the opportunities it faces while generating or developing many new resources. Therefore, an organization should devote the most time to resource management. One should bear in mind that organizations are always surrounded by high uncertainty. Developing new resources is vital for organizations to survive and stay one step ahead of competition (Crook, etc., 2008). The strategic planning process will give organizations the opportunity to effectively analyze their environment, and will allow them to tailor their plans to their environment. All this will result in a higher level of performance.

Recent research into the concept of organizational performance has highlighted that organizational performance does not have a one-dimensional structure, but should be measured by several different factors (Andersen, etc., 2016; Hubbard, 2009; Walker, etc., 2010). These factors include more "classical" concepts such as productivity, effectiveness and financial performance, as well as more relevant concepts such as social consequences and customer responsiveness. More importantly, organizational performance scientists have found many instances of the concept being influenced, especially by management, organization, and environment variables (Fisk, 2010; Walker and Andrews, 2015). As the concept of organizational performance is explored, more and more dimensions are emphasized. In this study, he outlines the relationship between organizational performance and productivity, efficiency, responsiveness, financial considerations.

Strategic planning is one of the chief issues of particular importance in modern educational institutions. Educational institutions generally recognize strategic planning as a method in the regeneration and development stages. Although educational institutions use strategic planning to boost performance, it should be recognized that this concept alone is not sufficient to improve performance (Andrews et.al., 2012).

In general, educational institutions, especially higher education institutions, have produced a number of studies, including strategic planning, which has been one of the foremost leaders of modern government concepts in the past period of self-improvement. The concept of development and innovation, as well as continuous work as an intellectual and administrative philosophy, focused on developing an organized and active strategy and intended to bring about desired changes. The important thing to notice here is that this

needs to be done in conjunction with the staff of the university. Joyce (1999) emphasized the need to plan for each component of the university and that strategizing would result in excessive concentration on performance. So strategy, as a tool for manipulating and shaping behavior, is true when it's actually implemented. Strategic planning is closely related to identifying organizational goals and objectives, designing policies and career plans, and choosing the organizational structure and administrative systems necessary to achieve these objectives and objectives. The strategic planning process is more than just a set of rules to be followed, and it expresses a philosophical approach to the business world (Dalal-Clayton and Bass, 2000).

Almost all scientists and communities interested in strategy have emphasized the importance of strategic planning. However, when this emphasis was made, they said that inequality in the sense of aspiration and abilities prevailed among institutions that were planning, implementing or developing strategic planning. It should be taken into account that some managers or leaders who make a strategic plan may be incomplete in their strategic thinking. Strategic planning was actually started to be implemented by many organizations. In some cases, a lot of deficiencies arise in the development of applications and theories. First, the first step in strategic planning, the transformation of organizations, comes with both a difficult and a long-term duration. This negativity has many institutions actually opting out of practice. It also means a very long process for strategic planning to show results. In general, strategic plans call for a continuous change, improvement, or perfection of institutions. Strategic planning has become an instrument of being better and more competitive for tertiary institutions, as is often called. Management has become much easier to deal with the challenges of today's conditions than strategic planning. The strategic planning of higher education institutions makes re-shaping institutions easier.

Conceptual Frame

In the 21st century, the size of firms was not important, but social changes around the world affected all the firms. Firms have become part of the global business world while being affected by developments and pressures. This can be attributed to a changing, dynamic, turbulent, unsustainable and highly competitive nature of the business climate. During this period, the relationship between business and society also experienced a significant change. The key drivers of this shift can be attributed to the globalization of trade, the increasing size and impact of corporate organizations, the repositioning of governments, the increasing strategic importance of stakeholder relations, knowledge and brand reputation (Olanipekun, 2015). The competitive business environment requires strategic planning and also requires resolution of the complexity of the decision-making process. Managing various activities is only part of the responsibilities of the modern administrator. The firm's near exterior reveals a second set of compelling factors. Administrators design strategic planning processes that they think will facilitate the proper positioning of a company in a competitive environment to effectively deal with everything affecting its growth ability. In the process of strategic planning, the firm's directors play a serious role. Strategic planning processes are being developed to more accurately forecast environmental changes and respond to unexpected competitive demands. Firms can therefore be prepared for domestic and international threats.

Porter (1985) argues that formulating a comprehensive strategy in his study is to link a company to its surroundings. Aremu (2010) argues that the strategy has many stakeholders. These stakeholders can be listed as stakeholders, suppliers, creditors, customers, and employees. Each one of these stakeholders has improved strategic planning, enabling firms to perform better, increasing employee loyalty. Strategic planning allows for the systematic management of change. It enables the organization to correctly deploy existing resources to serve a purpose.

In their work, Sharabati and Fuqaha (2014) brought to the literature that the strategic leadership was the most important practice in the age of globalization that separated the organizations. Strategic planning is being advocated as a key process for achieving vision, strategy and goals. Businesses involved in business need to carry out a specific strategic planning process to adapt to their environment, no matter what they do. Strategic planning is an area that involves the use of resources by managers, and deals with the major initiatives that are planned and emerging to enhance the performance of firms in their external environments (Nag et.al, 2007). Strategic planning and implementation includes determining the missions, visions, and objectives of firms, their projects, policies, plans, and the allocation of resources to implement the blueprints, projects, and programs designed to achieve these goals. Strategic planning and implementation, on the other hand, gives the business an overall direction.

The strategic planning activity can include not only the management tier but also the executive management units and all internal stakeholders within the firm. This coverage area is closely related to the structure of the account. Strategic planning encompasses the organization's mission, vision, and objectives, policies and plans, to identify projects, programs, and implement, and allocate resources that are usually designed to meet these goals.

Strategy and Strategic Planning

The basic strategy of a company can actually be defined as action plans to effectively and efficiently implement management activities. The creation of a strategy can aim to increase the business, attract more customers, ensure continuity, compete successfully, conduct management activities effectively, and improve the company's financial performance. Strategies, on the other hand, represent a management commitment to continue certain activities. Organizations without a strategy can be compared to a ship without a rudder (Thompson et.al, 2008). Strategic planning is one of the most valuable management tools for making corporate dreams come true. Organizations need to formulate and implement strategic plans in order to achieve their long-term goals, taking into account relevant internal and external environmental variables (Arnoldo and Majluf, 1991). A coherent strategic planning process includes enterprise activities and resource allocation needed to achieve enterprise strategic goals. Many private and public sector firms that are considered successful direct their visions and missions to their corporate decisions on resource allocation to compete. This is how they strengthen their competitive position.

Organizations operate in a dynamic, turbulent and ever-changing competitive environment as a result of environmental factors. The reasons for these markets are economic fluctuations, the development of new products and technologies, social changes, wars, globalization. As a result, both private and public institutions should be flexible and innovative in how they deal with the competition challenge and the unusual circumstances that customers face to meet their changing, complex needs. To be flexible and innovative, greater emphasis should be placed on strategic planning (Bumes, 2000).

A better understanding of the situation calls for a detailed description of what strategic planning is. There are many strategic planning definitions in the literature. This includes those who are more accepted than these definitions.

According to another definition by Sharplin and Mabry (1985), strategic planning is the vision of a desired future. In this planning the vision is widely defined. On the other hand, it is a process that expresses systematization of a range of activities to achieve goals or objectives. In contrast to long-term planning — which begins with the present situation and determines the way to meet future forecasted needs — strategic

planning begins with the desired end and returns to the current state. At every stage of long-term planning, the planner asks, "What should be done here to reach the next (higher) stage?" At every stage of strategic planning, he asks, "What should be done in the previous (sub) stage to get there?" In addition, unlike tactical planning - which focuses on meeting narrow defined intermediate goals with predefined tools - strategic planning looks at things more broadly and is flexible in choosing its tools. Another feature of strategic planning allows the organization to interact effectively with its environment. Elements of this interaction include political, social, technological, and economic elements.

A variety of strategic planning models have been developed by many researchers. The models proposed by these researchers include strategy planning, implementation of the organization's strategy, and strategic control focus. These researchers also stated that planning strategy and environmental analysis should be considered in the strategic planning stage (David and David, 2003).

It can be examined in three basic phases: mainly in the strategic planning process, planning, implementation and evaluation. It is important to note that these stages are divided into different ways by different scientists. The planning stage represents a strategic step in achieving the goals of organizations (Certo et.al, 1997). In a 2005 study, David stated that the formulation of strategies requires deciding what job to continue, how to allocate resources, and whether to enter international markets. The strategy is to develop missions, identify opportunities and threats, identify strengths and weaknesses (SWOT analysis), establish long-term goals, produce alternative strategies and select the best strategy to implement. This stage is also the implementation phase of strategic plans (Sharplin and Mabry, 1985), which began operations according to strategic plans. This phase also includes companies building goals, developing policies, motivating employees and allocating resources to implement strategies. Certo and. (1997) emphasizes that organizational analyzes of organizations need to be carried out effectively in order to determine the direction of organizations.

The final stage to be mentioned is the evaluation and control phase (Certo et.al, 1997), which allows information on the performance of strategic planning in the implementation phase and comparisons with existing standards. Assessment and control activities also allow for the review of existing strategies, measurement of performance, and corrective action. The evaluation of strategic plans and practices is important in the context of how institutions relate to what they have achieved today and what they will achieve tomorrow. One should bear in mind that success will always bring new and different problems. Institutions that are complacent about issues cannot sustain problems (David and David, 2003).

Performance

Performance Management in effect refers to the ongoing activities to achieve goals efficiently and efficiently (Cokins, 2009). Performance management can be measured using a wide range of criteria, including standards and indicators. These measurements clearly demonstrate opportunities for performance improvements. Optimal results are possible by performance measurement.

Performance management can focus on a broad range of areas, from the performance of an organization, a unit, or an employee, to even product or service generation processes. Business performance management enables organizations to set strategic goals and then measure performance according to their availability, according to Daniels (2006). Business performance management, on the other hand, incorporates a number of technology-supported management techniques and analytical processes. Core business performance includes

management processes, financial planning, operational planning, consolidation and reporting, business modeling, analysis, and tracking of key performance indicators associated with the strategy. As mentioned earlier, the strategy refers to the long-term process an organization seeks to maintain or improve its performance. Business performance management is permanent and unlikely to change significantly in the short term (Zajac and Shortell, 1989). Many studies strongly support this idea. Examples include works by Hannan and Freeman in 1984, Amburgey, etc., in 1990, and by Barnett and Freeman in 2001. The works are in the bibliography. Interested readers can find this work in the bibliography part of the study.

Works that highlight the relationship between strategy and business performance are included in the literature. Akpan (2000) argues that various measures for measuring organizational performance can be used. These criteria can be listed in the form of simple financial criteria such as return on investment, return on equity, profit margin, market share, equity debt, earnings per share, sales growth, and asset growth. All these values, however, do not appear to be sufficient alone to evaluate the success or failure of the strategy. Strategic planning studies carried out by Nmadu (2007) in Nigeria recognized the existence of the relationship between strategic management and organizational performance. The researcher named after him has shown that corporate financial performance tends to increase with a unit increase in strategic plan implementation levels. For all the financial performance indicators used (earnings per share, pretax profit, return on capital used, net asset, current operating capital ratio, increase in proportional market share, new product groups, total deposit), the performance of the institution has also tended to increase concurrently as the level of strategic planning increases.

In fact, strategic planning can make a significant difference to the performance of institutions. Basically, choosing strategic planning approaches where managers at all levels of a business interact in planning and implementation results in positive outcomes (David and David, 2003).

The relationship between strategy and performance was also seriously dealt with by Hammerers (1986). According to Hammerers (1986), performance improvement is a clear target of strategy. However, other approaches have also associated a wide range of outcomes (survival, learning, and so on) with performance, in addition to economic performance or in relation to economic performance.

In many empirical studies, he emphasizes the relationship between strategy and performance. For example, Miller and Friesen (1982) identified ten different strategic types. Six of these strategies have generally been characterized as successful (Adjustable Company at Medium Challenge, Adaptable Firm in a Very Challenging Environment, Dominant Firm, Under Fire Giant, Entrepreneur Holding, and Innovative Company). The remaining four strategies failed. Studies by Hambrick, Inc. in 1983 and by Miles, etc., in 1978 found significant performance differences among participants using strategy typologies. The general strategy literature also acknowledges the existence of performance differences. For example, Mascarenhas and Aaker (1989) found significant performance differences among strategic groups in the oil drilling industry, while Fiegenbaum and Thomas (1995) found meaningful differences between strategic groups in the insurance industry.

On the other hand, Cool and Schendel (1988) found some performance differences between groups in the pharmaceutical industry, but later concluded that strategic group effects were stronger than risk-return relationships. Nenkat and. (1990) in a study, they proved a relationship between resource distributions and performance. By distributing resources more differently than they should have, the firms have differentiated significantly in terms of performance levels. Natarjan. (1986) stressed that intercompany comparisons and performance differences are important. In this cross-sectional study involving many industries, Natarjan (1986)

found that the dimensions of aggression, analysis, defensiveness, reactivity and risk were associated with profitability.

Organizational performance is generally considered a term referring to for-profit organizations. Organizational performance includes expected outcomes, actual outcomes, or outcomes, of an organization measured against their goals or objectives. Experts interested in organizational performance consider institutional performance, including strategic planners, operations, financial or legal developments. In recent years, organizations have tried to manage their business performance by employing balanced points card methodology, in which more performance can be measured and monitored in multidimensional terms. These include financial performance (stock return), customer service, social responsibility (corporate leadership and community access), and employee management factors. As organizations grow, they improve in all senses and increase their interaction with other companies and organizations. Organizations had to choose to negotiate with other companies to expand their operations. The concept of organizational performance is needed right here. Because with organizational performance organizations can increase their impact, provide better, orderly response to deadlines, and produce quality work. For this reason, organizations strive to improve their organizational performance, invent new techniques that can improve their performance and help them improve themselves.

One technique discovered by scientists for improved organizational performance is the balanced points card method. In this way, the activities of an organization can be measured by vision and strategies. With this technical assistance, managers of the organizations gain a comprehensive view of the company's performance. In an overview of the organization's performance, business owners can improve areas that need improvement so they can get more done (Kaplan and Norton, 2005).

Organizational performance predictions of companies are also very important in light of these narratives. Because with the right organizational performance forecast, a business can both improve performance and drive business growth. Therefore, accurate detection of organizational performance is essential to productivity enhancement (www.managementperformanceadvice.com/orgperformance, Retrieved 27.05.2022).

When it comes to organizational performance, the method of benchmarking is more than a foregone issue. The benchmark introduces a general change in the structure of organizations and assists in achieving better results. The performance or objective of each part/unit of a business or organization is determined beforehand. Then a measurement is set as standard for performance comparison. Performance or effort is compared to defined standards and this process is called benchmarking. The main purpose of the benchmark is to compare what is achieved with other metrics or standard scales and evaluate performance results. The benchmark can also be performed between organizations or companies in the same sector (Webometrics, 2004, Web Ranking of World Universities, 2010).

Education in Libya

Libya is an Arab country situated in North Africa on the southern coast of the Mediterranean. Libya's economy can be associated largely with oil, in that it has many oil reserves. The total area of the country is about 1,759,540 square kilometers. It also has the longest coastline of any Mediterranean country, with a length of about 1.955 km. Libya's neighbors are listed as follows. In the east, Egypt in the southeast, Sudan in the south, Chad and Niger in the west, Algeria in the west, and Tunisia in the northwest. Libya is also a country that is a member of many associations as a result of its neighborly relations and international relations. They can be ranked as United Nations, African Union, Arab Maghreb Union, Arab States League, Non-Aligned Movement,

Organization of Islamic Conference and OPEC (The People's Committee for Education, 2001; Oxford Business Group, 2008).

The population of Libya is not very large, compared to the official figures for the country. The total population of the country is 6,310,434, according to official records. This number also includes tens of thousands of people who emigrated to and are not actually Libyan citizens (Hanley, 2001) to search for business opportunities due to the attractive offers offered to foreign professionals at universities and tertiary institutions. Despite such emigration from the outside, the population is still small.

The Libyan government has implemented a development program (Hanley, 2001) that seeks to promote, improve and modernize the infrastructure of education and understanding. Libya's education secretary, who served in 2000, emphasized that education, health and social services are the top priorities in developing Libya's infrastructure.

According to the study published by Hanley in 2001, the Gaddafi Development Foundation took on the responsibility of developing the educational system and infrastructure in Libya, and subsequently, efforts were undertaken to modernize and strengthen 5,000 schools and colleges. This development includes the creation of model training institutions for the future generation of Libya. Efforts have been made to recruit equipment and specialists at every level. Additionally, the agenda for this program includes the following points:

- Improvement of curricula in schools and universities, including scientific journals, periodicals, and books.
- Opening the door to unifying Libyans in the global community through many programs — such as providing young Libyans the opportunity to continue studying abroad and to achieve international qualifications.
- The launch of an 18-month plan to provide one million computers to a million Libyan children.
- Integrating Libya into the global educational community with its vast Internet network.
- Activation of education hospitals
- Educate and activate young entrepreneurs to help them succeed in their new endeavors.
- The realization of the e-government system.
- Opening the door for co-operation between international education institutions and drafting programs to improve cooperation.
- To fund Libya's educational development.
- Providing foreign scholarships to students in order to quality their education abroad. Among the main countries are Britain, Canada, the United States, Malaysia, Egypt and Australia.

By 1980, in order to correct this situation, the Libyan government legalized the program known as the "New Educational Structure". This program restructured the school curricula in favor of technical issues, and specific emphasis was placed on Arabic language and Quran education in humanities. In addition, from the seventh grade, English instruction was also compelled to keep up with developments in the world. The introduction of traditional high school schools at the high school level, as well as professional and technical schools that further specialize. At the same time, new educational reforms have carried out applications with an emphasis on technical and vocational education at the higher education level. By the 2000s, Libya had seen a significant increase in the number of high technical and professional schools. The General Public Education Committee and the Occupational Education Committee have been dissolved, and the transfer of responsibilities and responsibilities to regional public committees has been legalized (Libya Undersecretariat for National Education, 2000).

According to The Economist (2009), most of the governments in the Arabian Peninsula are aware of the fact that their university and school systems are in poor shape. The responsible governments of Arab countries, including Libya, have been waging a sustained struggle for the improvement of their educational infrastructure and facilities. The number of college students has been 13,418 in the past, while by 1996 students accounted for 27% of Libya's population. But a good part of these students are the migrant students who come with their parents to Libya and participate in the education institutions. At present, the number of students in elementary and secondary education is growing rapidly. The new educational reforms were introduced in 1980, aimed at changing the curricula of schools, beginning the Arabic language and Koran studies, and promoting technical issues in addition to the humanities. He emphasized the opening of vocational and technical schools in secondary school, as well as traditional schools. This strategy also emphasized the opening of technical and professional institutions (Teferra and Altbach, 2003; Yousefi, etc., 2006), which contributed significantly to the development of these regions in different parts of the country.

The educational system that existed in the past in Libya was the model 6-3-3. This model of education states that education began at age 6 and that elementary school lasted six years, followed by three years as a middle school and three years as a high school. The system now exists, which specializes in 2 years of kindergarten, 9 years of basic education, and 3 or 4 years of secondary education (Clark, 2010). Eventually, the successful candidates obtain a "General Secondary School" certificate or, alternatively, a technical school diploma. Adequate and highly successful, sixteen institutions, nine universities, and seven higher education institutions qualify to continue higher education (Al Gamatti, 2005).

And Sophie. (2009) The Libyan government is currently working on implementing one of the largest educational projects in the country. The government is about to implement the largest university building program in the world, with the goal of motivating future generations to choose and work in their own countries rather than receiving education in other countries. Another reason for this project is to reduce the number of highly motivated and bright students who have left the country in the last few years in order to pursue higher university degrees. As part of this project, in 2006 the Ministry of Education drafted a five-year strategic plan to improve the country's educational facilities and infrastructure, starting in 2008. In 2007, the Organization for Development of Administrative Centers, responsible for strategic infrastructure projects, announced plans to build and develop 25 Libyan universities. New strategic partnership initiatives have been undertaken between universities in Libya and successful foreign universities in order to improve the education system. Examples include a partnership between Sabha University in Libya and Heriot-Watt University in the United Kingdom and Edinburgh.

Higher Education in Libya

Sophie et.al. (2009), they argued that the rapidly increasing number of students at each level of education should also increase in the number of educational institutions, particularly higher education institutions. For example, the number of universities increased from two universities in 1975 to nine universities in 2003, with the number of technical and professional institutes reaching 84 since 1980. The first university in Libya started teaching in Benghazi in 1951. The primary purpose of universities in that period is to provide education to teachers of secondary schools, to develop the capacities of students and government employees.

Then in 1957 the College of Economics and Commerce, 1962 the Faculty of Law, 1966 the Faculty of Agriculture began their education. The expansion continued in 1970 with the opening of the Faculty of Medicine, Al-Bayda Islamic University, and with the development of oil production, the Faculty of Petroleum and Mineral Engineering was established in 1972. The University of Libya was divided into two universities in 1973. This is the University of Tripoli and the University of Benghazi. These universities are now called

Al-Fatah University in Tripoli and Gar-Yuns University in Benghazi. In the following years, the number of universities was increased, and universities were undergoing new educational reforms to allow them to study the increasing number of students. The number of universities increased to 13 in 1995. Higher education in Libya is also encouraging talented and intellectual people to emigrate to Libya and participate in educational institutions (Al-Shapani, 2001).

For this reason, higher education in Libya is offered in both public and private universities and higher education institutes. Since 2000, the country's public committees have served as the body responsible for the management of education in the Libyan regions (Teferra & Altbach, 2003). In Libya, higher education is administered by the People's Committee of Higher Education, while each university is administered by its own People's Committee. This public committee includes secretaries, department heads and deans. The faculty board serves as a direct member of the faculty secretaries' University People's Committee. There are also Student Community Councils to manage students' businesses and activities. Introduced by higher education institutes and university colleges, the private sector and the local public administration (Shabiat), it was ultimately built by local government officials in 1997-2000 to address the quality and needs of education through developments in more than five private universities (Al Falugi, 2008).

Post-Gaddafi Period (2011 to Present)

The 2011 civil war sparked criticism of many institutions and functions, a criticism reflected in the educational system. In the educational system and programs implemented especially during the Gaddafi era, there have been severe criticism and many errors have come to light. According to the Tripoli Post, a major Libyan newspaper, students at the University of Tripoli complained at the time that the Gaddafi regime provided them with low quality education.

Following this period of internal turmoil and a proliferation of criticism, the newly appointed Education Ministry began its efforts to rewrite the curriculum. In January 2012, new curricula and texts were introduced. In the interim regime, many practices were implemented to eliminate the temporary impact on education levels and to allow for the removal of deficiencies. Suliman Al-Sahli was appointed acting education minister, emphasizing the need for an objective training program.

Vocational training with the Gaddafi regime in the country has become highly focused on local and public sector jobs. Shifting this focus to private sector jobs and implementing practices to improve international relations has become a key issue for Libya's newly-elected government. Libya's Technical and Professional Training Council signed an agreement with British-based TVET BK in 2013 to facilitate efforts to modernize institutions and overhaul professional education established in the 1970s and 1980s. TVET BK has agreed to set up UK-based workshops to speed the transition of skilled workers to the private sector. In May 2013, the General National Congress launched the financial program to send students to study programs abroad. 2,004 educators and 5,692 pupils were selected for this program, with the number rising to 3,616 over the coming years. As part of the same program, 31,000 students were to be sent abroad to study English language. This program initially gave priority to students struggling during the civil war, and was expanded over time to allow women and disabled students to receive scholarships.

History of Higher Education in Tripoli, Libya

Tripoli university education in Libya dates back to the independence won in 1951. Then the university education life began to develop, with the University of Tripoli divided into the campuses of Benghazi and

Tripoli. After many years on the campuses, several faculties have been established, including the Faculty of Arts and Education, Science, Economics and Commerce, Law and Agriculture. In 1967, both the Faculty of High Technical Research and the Faculty of Engineering and Education began teaching at these universities. In 1970, the Faculty of Medicine, Arabic, and Islamic Sciences began to recruit students.

As previously mentioned, the University of Tripoli and the University of Benghazi were divided into two separate, independent universities in 1973. These universities are then renamed as Al-Fatah University and Gar-Yuns University respectively. Due to the increased number of students enrolled in higher education during the 1980s and 1990s, the two universities were restructured and increased with different universities. In recent years, due to some policy changes, it has been decided to reduce the number of universities to nine again. Furthermore, under new policies, university education is considered non-central and specialized universities. Although no formal study of the distribution of student records at Libyan universities has been conducted, there is a lack of equilibrium between the number of students enrolled in humanities and arts, and the number of students in science and technology (Teferra and Altbach, 2003).

To be eligible for admission to both university and non-university programs in Libya, there must be at least one Secondary Education Certificate. Since 1990, all universities have proposed that 65 percent or higher of secondary education exams be achieved as a condition for enrollment in a program. Some faculties, such as medicine and engineering, require scores of over 75 percent for admission. Students with an average of less than 65 percent are admitted to higher education and vocational institutions. Students from specialized secondary schools are encouraged to maintain their specialty.

Results and Suggestions

The study found that strategic management and implementation have significant implications for business performance. Preferring the right strategic implications is an effective way of maximizing the performance of organizations as a whole, not just as an individual. The study therefore emphasizes that strategic planning practices must be taken seriously in order to achieve sustainable and high business performance.

Recommendations developed based on the study's findings may be listed as follows;

- 1st Academic and administrative staff of Libyan universities need to develop a strategic planning model in order to improve the institution's competitiveness.
- 2nd The universities serving in Libya need to adopt the right competitive strategies. So they can take steps that can have advantages both over their competitors and at the global level.
- 3RD It should promote positive cultural interaction with international universities, promote international research centers, and promote agreements with select universities.
- 4th It is necessary to strengthen the loyalty of the staff serving in every facet of the university to the institution.
- 5TH The motivations of academics working in the university should be increased.
- 6TH Courses, seminars and training must be provided to develop the skills of the professors in strategic planning of the universities serving in Libya.

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